

Absenteeism in undergraduate medical students - a cross sectional study from Central India

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ABSTRACT

Background: Absenteeism at higher education level affects the learning process and eventually final result of the students. Low academic achievement assumes critical importance particularly for medical and health care providers who are concerned with decision making in situations involving urgent life and death matters. Identifying the student level reasons for absenteeism is the first step in handling this problem.

Methods: The present study was descriptive cross sectional in nature conducted at a Medical College in central India. Medical students of MBBS were the study participants. Data collection was done with the help of a pre designed self administered questionnaire. Statistical analysis was performed with the help of open Epi info.

Results: All the 198 study participants were in the age group of 20 to 23 years with a mean of 21.25 ± 0.79 years. Male and female students were almost similar in numbers. Hostel related and curriculum related factors had a major impact on absenteeism.

Conclusions: The reasons for absenteeism in medical students are manifold and hence the approaches to tackle them should be multidimensional. This realisation on part of both students and faculties is imperative for achieving a fruitful solution to this accrescent problem.

Key words: Reasons, Medical, MBBS, Absenteeism, students

Introduction:

Absenteeism no matter what the cause be, has emerged as a daunting problem in the classrooms worldwide. With the increasing trend of private coaching classes and easy availability of online study material the absenteeism has increased manifold. Medical colleges are no exception to this. With the revolutionary development in the field of electronics¹ various computer software are available to make lectures more presentable, interesting and interactive, thus making the traditional teaching

more effective.² Despite this development low attendance at lectures is still an issue.^{3,4} Classroom attendance remains a key determinant of academic performance. Previous empirical literature suggests that student performance is inversely correlated with absenteeism. Absenteeism at higher education level affects the learning process and eventually final result of the students.⁵ Low academic achievement assumes critical importance particularly for medical and health care providers who are concerned with decision making in situations involving urgent life and death matters.^{6,7} In spite of implementing strict policies, the rate of absenteeism remains high and is a cause of great concern.⁸ Identifying the student level reasons for absenteeism is the first step in

handling this problem. Early detection and prevention might prevent unwanted consequences of absenteeism on medical student's academic performance. Hence the present study was conducted to find the reasons for the same as reported by them.

Material and methods

The present study was descriptive cross sectional and was conducted at a medical college from Central India. The study participants were final MBBS part-I students. All 201 students of the batch were included for the study and thus universal sampling was applied. Before starting the study approval was taken from institutional ethics committee (IEC) of the college. The nature and the purpose of the study was explained to the study subjects in detail and written informed

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consent was obtained. Due care was taken to ensure confidentiality and anonymity. The questionnaire did not include any personal information.

Data collection tool was a pre designed and pretested questionnaire which included questions regarding reasons for absenteeism. The study participants were also instructed to grade the various reasons (personal, teaching related, college related, hostel related and curriculum related) on a 5 point Likert scale wherein a score of 1 denoted strongly negative impact, 2 was for weak negative impact, 3 meant no impact, 4 stood for weak positive impact and 5 represented a strong positive impact. Data entry was done in Microsoft excel. Statistical analysis was performed with the help of open Epi info. Descriptive data was expressed as mean and percentage.

Results:

Of the 201 students, 198 responded to the questionnaire. All the study participants were in the age group of 20 to 23 years with a mean of 21.25 ± 0.79 years. The number of male and female students was almost equal. The socio demographic details of the study participants are shown in table 1.

Table 1. Socio demographic Information of study participants:

Socio demographic variable	Number	Percentage
Age in years		
20	29	14.65
21	99	50.00
22	60	30.30
23	10	5.05
Gender		
Female	100	50.51
Male	98	49.49
Socio economic status		
I	68	34.34
II	77	38.89
III	23	11.62
IV	24	12.12
V	6	3.03
Current residence		
Hostel campus	122	61.62
Own home	28	14.14
Rented room	28	14.14

The study participants were asked if they think that being absent in the classes is a problem. The responses for the same are shown in figure 1.

Figure 1 Perception about absenteeism as a problem

The present study attempted to identify the impact of various reasons on absenteeism. For the sake of better understanding these reasons each of which had a score of 1 to 5 were grouped into personal, teaching related, college related, hostel related and curriculum related. The mean of the scores for each category of reasons impacting absenteeism were calculated as per their responses on the Likert scale. It was observed that hostel related and curriculum related factors had a major impact. Mean scores for each category of reasons are shown in figure 2.

Figure 2 Reasons impacting absenteeism

Foremost among the personal factors influencing absenteeism were attending class for post graduate entrance, going to bed late due to studies or due

to excessive use of social media, preference for self studies, mass bunking, illness of self or a family member all with a mean score above 3.

Teaching related factors of paramount importance in influencing absenteeism were monotonous teaching, less focus on practical applicability, lack of interaction, poor teaching skills and excessive use / no use of audio-visual aids with mean scores of 3.25, 3.05, 3.00, 2.71, and 2.70 respectively. Salient college

related factors identified were poor infrastructure (3.17), no provision of preparation leave (3.17) and poor classroom ambience (3.17). Some other important reasons identified in this category were frequent last moment cancellation of classes (3.03), lack of reading rooms (3.03) and no penalty for absenteeism (2.44).

Cardinal hostel related factors were sanitation problems (3.6), food related problems (3.52), non functional washrooms (3.47), mosquito menace (3.43) and water

scarcity (3.29). Vast curriculum (3.63), no proper coverage of syllabus in the lecture series (3.37) and lectures not catering to future needs (3.09) were the noteworthy curriculum related factors.

Main reasons in all the categories as per their relative importance in influencing absenteeism are displayed in table 2. Attending class for PG entrance, preferring self studies, sanitation and food related problems were amongst the common influencers.

Table 2. Common reasons for absenteeism

Reasons	Strong negative impact (1) No. (%)	Weak negative impact (2) No. (%)	No impact (3) No. (%)	Weak positive impact (4) No. (%)	Strongly positive impact (5) No. (%)
Attending class for PG entrance	13 (6.57)	23 (11.62)	46 (23.23)	59 (29.80)	57 (28.79)
Going to bed late due to studies	9 (4.55)	27 (13.64)	61 (30.81)	68 (34.34)	33 (16.67)
Prefer self studies	19 (9.60)	26 (13.13)	64 (32.32)	34 (17.17)	55 (27.78)
Vast curriculum	18 (9.09)	11 (5.56)	50 (25.25)	66 (33.33)	53 (26.77)
Syllabus not covered in lectures	23 (11.62)	17 (8.59)	65 (32.83)	50 (25.25)	43 (21.72)
Lectures not catering to future needs	27(13.64)	28 (14.14)	73 (36.87)	40 (20.20)	30 (15.15)
Sanitation problems	22 (11.11)	17 (8.59)	46 (23.23)	45 (22.73)	68 (34.34)
Food related problems	23 (11.62)	15 (7.58)	52 (26.26)	51 (25.76)	57 (28.79)
Non functional washrooms	22 (11.11)	25 (12.63)	50 (25.25)	40 (20.20)	61 (30.81)
No provision of preparation leave	25 (12.63)	37 (18.69)	49 (24.75)	42 (21.21)	45 (22.73)
Classroom ambience	23 (11.62)	24 (12.12)	79 (39.90)	41 (20.71)	31 (15.66)
Poor infrastructure	28 (14.14)	30 (15.15)	54 (27.27)	51 (25.76)	35 (17.68)

Monotonous teaching	25 (12.63)	27 (13.64)	53 (26.77)	59 (29.80)	34 (17.17)
Less focus on practical applicability	33 (16.67)	32 (16.16)	56 (28.28)	45 (22.73)	32 (16.16)
No interaction/ rapport between students – teachers	31 (15.66)	28 (14.14)	71 (35.86)	45 (22.73)	23 (11.62)
Going late to bed due to social media	36 (18.18)	31 (15.66)	44 (22.22)	48 (24.24)	39 (19.70)
Peer pressure	34 (17.17)	37 (18.69)	60 (30.30)	51 (25.76)	16 (8.08)
Mass bunk	21 (10.61)	32 (16.16)	72 (36.36)	39 (19.70)	34 (17.17)

Discussion:

Medical curriculum being extremely vast demands thorough understanding of the subject which is not always possible only by reading the books and other available material on the subject. The importance of good attendance in classes for academic achievement is a well known fact.⁹ However due to various reasons the attendance in the medical colleges is decreasing. Available literature also indicates that attendance from lectures and tutorials is on a declining trend globally thus making absenteeism a topic to be addressed urgently.^{10,11} It is vital that the reasons for absenteeism among the medical students of a given set up are identified so that authorities can take measures to solve the problem. Majority of the participants of the present study felt that absenteeism is a problem. This indicates a good attitude as the medical students have an insight about the problem of absenteeism. This can help in their contribution towards handling this issue.

Regarding reasons for absenteeism in the medical students in the present study numerous personal factors came

ahead. Important amongst these were going late to bed on account of numerous causes and attending post graduate coaching as reported to have a positive influence by around half of the respondents. These personal factors have also been reported as an important reason for absenteeism in medical schools by other studies.^{9,11} Mass bunk and peer pressure for not attending classes were also considered to have a positive (weak and positive both together) influence on absenteeism in the present study. Gul R et al in a Peshawar based survey have also mentioned the role of peer pressure causing absenteeism.⁹ Many times the late night group studies result in going to bed late at night leading to sleepiness in the morning hours and eventually absenteeism. The current Competency Based Medical Education (CBME) with its foundation course may serve as a cornerstone in overcoming this by establishing a good student rapport with their teachers and inculcating discipline.

The present generation medical students who are habituated with a techno savvy and comfortable life may find the classroom ambience difficult to adjust specially in an

old government set up like the one in the present study. This reflected in on third responses conveying classroom ambience and poor infrastructure as a reason for absenteeism thus making college related factors a contributor. Poor classroom management as a cause of absenteeism was also observed by Bhandari MH et al in their study.¹² Rao BT et al in a study from Andhra Pradesh, India have also highlighted similar college related factors having an impact on absenteeism.¹³ However the role of such factors is in contrast with another study wherein no one mentioned about infra-structure like ambience and lecture hall as the reason for non attendance. This is justified as the afore mentioned study was conducted in a private medical college whereas the current study setting was government medical college.

In the present study approximately one third of the study participants expressed that teaching related factors such as monotonous teaching and no interaction between students-teachers have a positive impact on absenteeism. Correct use of audio-visual aids and interactive sessions can help tackle this issue very

well. This is coherent with the findings in other studies also.^{11,14}

The present study showed that hostel related factors were among the main reasons for not attending the classes as reflected in the maximum mean score. Role of hostel related factors is also reported in another study.¹¹ The impact of food related problems in hostellers is justified in the present study as the medical institute is located in central India and it has an intake of students from all over the country having diversity of eating habits not which may not always be fulfilled by the hostel mess. Many a times these students tend to eat outside food other than the hostel mess resulting in gastrointestinal upsets leading to absenteeism.

Curriculum related factors such as vast curriculum were the next common reason for absenteeism as reported to have a positive impact by more than half of the study participants. This at times makes the medical students confused who refrain from actual attending the classes and instead prefer to read the topics due to the probable apprehension that they may not be able to read the entire study material on the subject. This explains the preference for self-studies as reported by approximately half of the study participants. These findings are coherent with other studies.^{9, 11, 14}

Thus the current questionnaire based survey has put forth various reasons for absenteeism in the medical students which can be utilised to tackle the problem and hence can be considered as the strength of the study. However it has focused only on identifying the role of these reasons of absenteeism. The study has limitations of cross sectional study. Moreover it was conducted in a single institute.

More studies in different institutes and including role of interventions may be conducted in future.

Conclusions:

It can be concluded from the present study that the reasons for absenteeism in medical students are manifold and hence the approaches to tackle them should be multidimensional. This realisation on part of both students and faculties is imperative for achieving a fruitful solution to this accrescent problem. Minor changes like improving student teacher interactions and providing a conducive environment at both college and hostels can go a long way in solving this mammoth problem.

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